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Role of Women in Environment Conservation

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Introduction

Women symbolize nature in Indian society. She creates and nurtures the creation of the bloom. She signifies Shakti, the power that derives the system. It is true that the status of Indian women has eroded significantly. Nevertheless twenty century saw reawakening and a steady of upswing, which is largely attributable to spread of education and social reform.

There are many activities which women perform are responsible for degradation of environment. Women collect food, wood from forest, they also use water for domestic purpose and also responsible for management of domestic waste, garbage etc. Hence, they can play vital role in environment conservation by adopting proper management of domestic use of water, substitution of fuel wood, proper disposal of domestic waste/garbage.

Traditional women have been responsible for subsistence and survival for fuel fodder and habitat, though they rarely get the credit for nurturing these life support systems. Added to these environmental destruction, exacerbates women's problems in a way very difficult from that of men. The challenge is to re-establish the symbiosis between communities, women and nature resources and reverse the trend of the negative impact of existing developmental paradigms.

Women have always been the principle

conservers of bio-diversity. Even today they perform duties such as seed selection, multiplication and conservation. The on-farm conservation traditions of rural and tribal women, with reference to agro-biodiversity are well known. Unfortunately, current food security system depends on too few crops. It is important to expand the basis of food security by including large numbers of spices and varieties of food plants still maintained by tribal and rural families. For this purpose, women can be trained in the revitalization of the on-farm conservation traditions of the older generation through biotechnological process. The training should also include equipping them for compiling bio-diversity inventories and for taking decision on issues like giving consent to using their genetic material by breeding companies / institutions.

Traditionally, women have dealt with non-monetized biomass based subsistence economy of the household i.e. firewood, cow dung, crop wastes, organic manure, etc. In comparison men tend to destroy nature to earn cash even if it means creating hardship in their own families for their womenfolk to collect fuel and fodder e.g. sale of herbs and wood. The upshot is that women work as unpaid labourers on family farms with a greater role than men in operational decision making. The population pressure has increased male migration, which in turn adds to the women's work load. In effect this means that

women's responsibilities extend from the household duties to working in the fields as well. A destructive chain reaction emerges. As the time required for fuel and fodder collection grows and firewood becomes scarce, cow-dung previously spread on the fields, is used in the kitchen, thereby depleting soil resources and causing a negative effect on the livelihood of local people and environment.

It is common knowledge throughout the world that the growth of technology and the processes of commercialization, industrialization and globalization affect men and women differently. The world realizes, clearly today that real development cannot take roots if it by-passes women, who not only represent half of the humanity, but represents the very kernel around which social change takes shape. Therefore, as India embarks on bold and sweeping economic reforms, concern for women and efforts to mainstream them occupy the centre stage.

Beijing Declaration¹ and United Nation Declaration² have accepted the importance of women in environment conservation. The points of United Declaration, titled Environment Programme 2005³ are following:

1. In many countries women are at the forefront of campaigns to conserve natural resources: examples include India's Chipko movement to protect forests and a scheme in Brazil to combat desertification.
2. The situation of women is characterized by lack of ownership and control over land and resources, and limited access to education and services.
3. Rural women contribute by providing food, fuel, medicinal remedies and necessary raw materials, but their traditional knowledge is being threatened by biodiversity loss and

4. Severe environmental degradation, particularly in drylands, puts extra burdens on women, who are often left behind to run households when men migrate.
5. Water is central to household and income-generating activities for women, but water shortage, pollution and other problems with access (land tenure, affordability) mean that gender issues are crucial to all projects and policies concerning water resources.

The commitments made at international agreements, particularly the Convention on Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), need to be implemented. Specifically, UNEP argues for: -

- gender analysis at organizational, programme and project levels in natural resources conservation and management, and implementation of their recommendations.
- the preservation of women's knowledge, along with the prevention of piracy and commercialization of local and traditional knowledge.

Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, the Millennium Development and Goals and the Johannesburg Plan of Implementation (2002).

The Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action identified three strategic objectives in the critical area of women and the environment:

- Involve women actively in environmental decision-making at all levels.
- Integrate gender concerns and perspectives in policies and programmes for sustainable development.
- Strengthen or establish mechanisms at the national, regional and international levels to

assess the impact of development and environmental policies on women.

Following the 5-year review of the Beijing Platform for Action, major achievements in the field of women and the environment are:

- A positive, albeit tentative, trend towards greater participation and involvement of women in environmental decision-making positions.
- Steps to incorporate a gender perspective in (inter) national and local environmental activities, policies, plans and legislation, as well as in institutional arrangements.
- Increase in women's capabilities in the environmental field, including their knowledge, skills and organization.
- A growing quantity and quality of gender-sensitive environmental research and data.
- A more holistic approach that incorporates poverty eradication and women's economic empowerment in environmental conservation and management.

Arun Nigavenkar⁴ in his book reflect the basic trends of administrative structure, models, activities, planning, programmes and projects adopted by the government regarding environmental conservation and developments in India.

Brenda Cranney⁵ in his book entitled, "Local Environment and Lived Experience" analysed the strategies adopted towards livelihood maintenance at the levels of individual, household and other organized groups of people organize their basic material existence holds a central position, namely the production and provision of basic needs such as food, water shelter, energy, furnishing and clothing.

Though the Government of India is working towards an environmentally sound and sustainable quality of life, the problems,

challenges and issues are multi-faceted. However, women in India are playing a crucial role in protection and conservation of environment. Women in our country have brought a different perspective to the environment debate, because of their different experience base. Poor women's lives are not compartmentalized and they see the issues in a broad and holistic perspective. They understand clearly that economics and environment are compatible. Their experience reveals to them that soil, water and vegetation, necessary for their day-to-day living, requires care and good management. Environmental degradation is related not only to the biosphere alone, but to the social sphere as well.

Keeping in view the inherent capabilities of women in the management as well as the need for women entrepreneurship development, educational and vocational training in various fields, communication skills, creativity and innovation, quality management and control, inventory and production management need to be strengthened throughout the length and breadth of the country. To achieve this, resources and strength of women need to be channelized to develop their full potential so as to take their rightful place as equal partners in all spheres.

References :

1. Women and Environment', Report by the United Nations Environment Programme, 2005.
2. Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action, The Millennium Development Goals and the Johannesburg Plan of Implementation, 2002.
3. Women in Environmental Conservation,' A Project Report, PWA, 2005.
4. Nigavekar Arun (2003), Environmental Conservation and Sustainable Development, Anamika Publishers, New Delhi.
5. Cranney Brenda (2001), Local Environment and lived experience.